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Novel Gene Biomarkers Specific to Human Mesenchymal Stem Cells Isolated from Bone Marrow

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Abstract: In this paper, we present a comparative analysis of the transcriptomic profile of three different human cell types: hematopoietic stem cells (HSCs), bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) and fibroblasts (FIBs). The work aims to identify unique genes that are differentially expressed as specific markers of bone marrow-derived MSCs, and to achieve this undertakes a detailed analysis of three independent datasets that include quantification of the global gene expression profiles of three primary cell types: HSCs, MSCs and FIBs. A robust bioinformatics method, called *GlobalTest*, is used to assess the specific association between one or more genes expressed in a sample and the outcome variable, that is, the ‘cell type’ provided as a single univariate response. This outcome variable is predicted for each sample tested, based on the expression profile of the specific genes that are used as input to the test. The precision of the tests is calculated along with the statistical sensitivity and specificity for each gene in each dataset, yielding four genes that mark MSCs with high accuracy. Among these, the best performer is the protein-coding gene Transgelin (TAGLN, Gene ID: 6876) (with a Positive Predictive Value > 0.96 and FDR < 0.001), which identifies MSCs better than any of the currently used standard markers: ENG (CD105), THY1 (CD90) or NT5E (CD73). The results are validated by RT-qPCR, providing novel gene biomarkers specific for human MSCs.

Keywords: cell marker; transcriptomic; stem cell; Mesenchymal cell; MSC; fibroblast; gene expression; CD marker; hematopoietic cell; bioinformatics

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1. Introduction

Fibroblasts (FIBs) are present in the stromal component of every organ and are the main providers of the extracellular matrix, mainly collagen, that maintains their structure [1]. Mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs), also known in some forums as Mesenchymal stromal cells, constitute a non-hematopoietic population that reside in various cellular tissues, mainly bone marrow and adipose tissue. They have fibroblastic appearance when they adhere to